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ТАЪЛИМ КЕЛАЖАГИ: МАЪМУН УНИВЕРСИТЕТИДА ИННОВАЦИОН ҲОЯЛАР.....8

FILOLOGIYA

1. Omanboyeva Aziza Doniyor qizi
TURLI DINIY TA'LIMOTLARDA "ZUHD" TUSHUNCHASIGA DOIR QARASHLARNI
O'RGANISHNING AYRIM DOLZARB MASALALARI//.....11

2. Shomurodova Maftuna
SADRIDDIN AYNII YARATGAN DARSLIKLAR XUSUSIDA.....15

3. Ismailova Feruza Ismailovna
MAQOL VA MATALLARDA QOFIYA VA MA'NO.....19

4. Karimov Hikmatbek Anvar o'g'li
RUS XALQI SHAKLLANISHINI ILK BOSQICHDAGI TIL VAZIYATI.....24

5. Raximbayev Musobek Komiljon o'g'li
OGAHIY "TA'VIZU-L-OSHIQIN" DEVONINING MATN KORPUSINI
SHAKILLANTIRISHDA MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....29

IQTISODIYOT

1.Файзиёв Ойбек Рахимович
АЙЛАНМА МАБЛАҒЛАР САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШНИНГ МУҲИМ ОМИЛИ...34

2. Rasulova Nigora Yusupovna
ATTITUDES OF TOURISTS TOWARDS ENVIRONMENTAL SOLUTIONS: A SURVEY OF
TOURISTS IN UZBEKISTAN.....39

3. Vaisov Dilshod Ibodullayevich
RAQOBATBARDOSHLIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY
ASOSLARI.....43

4. Karimboev Dilshod Davronbek o'g'li
THE FUTURE OF SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORTATION IN THE KHOREZM REGION.....50

5. Jumaniyozov Feruzbek Dilshod o'g'li
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASINING SHAKLLANISHI VA UNING MAMLAKAT
IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI.....56

6. Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna
XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA AKTIVLARNI HISOBGA OLISHNI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....61

7. Matkarimova Intizor Atabaevna Matkuliyeva Sanabar Ismailovna
GLOBALIZATSIYA SHAROITIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA MILLIY HISOBLAR
TIZIMINI UYG'UNLASHTIRISHNING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....67

PEDAGOGIKA

1. Qalandarova Iroda Hamdam qizi

BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIDA TANQIDIY FIKRLASHNI
SHAKLANTIRISHNING AYRIM PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI.....74

2. Djabbarova Nilufar Baxtiyarovna

ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TADQIQOTLARDA LIDERLIK MASALASINING
O'RGANILISHNING ARIM O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI HUSUSIDA.....79

PSIXOLOGIYA

1. Ulug'ova Shahlola Musliddinovna

QADRIYATLARNING TADBIRKORLAR FAOLIYATIDAGI ROLI.....85

2. Djumaniyozova Muxayya Xusinovna

QADRIYAT FENOMENINING PSIXOLOGIYADA O'RGANILISHI.....90

3. Ўктамova Шохида Одилбек қизи

ВОЯГА ЕТМАГАНЛАР ЖИНОЯТЧИЛИГИ МУАММОСИНИ ЎРГАНИШ-ПСИХОЛОГИК
ТАДҚИҚОТ ПРЕДМЕТИ СИФАТИДА.....96

TARIX

1. Davletov Sanjarbek Rajabovich

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MADANIY DIPLOMATIYASIDA YUNESKO BILAN
HAMKORLIK ALOQALARINING O'RNI.....102

2. Djabborova Adolatxon Kazakbayevna

XORAZM VOHASI ZIYORATGOHLARIDA O'TKAZILADIGAN MAROSIMLARNING
AN'ANAVIY MANA'VIY MADANIYATDA TUTGAN O'RNI VA ULARNING MILLIY
MENTALITETGA TA'SIRI.....108

3. Асанова Светлана Алексеевна

ТУРКИСТОН ДАВРИ ЁҚУББЕК ДАВЛАТИНИНГ ВОРИСЛАРИ (1877-1881 й.й).....113

4. Аубакирова Жанна Сакеновна. Алексеенко Александр Николаевич, Столярова

Элеонора Олеговна, Краснобаева Нелли Леонидовна
КАЗАХСТАН В НАЧАЛЕ 30-х гг. XX ВЕКА: ДЕМОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ ПОТЕРИ
КАЗАХСКОГО НАРОДА.....122

5. Дилафруз Ийманова

ИНЖЕНЕР-ТЕХНИК КАДРЛАРНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШНИНГ СОВЕТ АМАЛИЁТИ:
МУАММОЛАР ВА НАТИЖАЛАР (1930-1941 йиллар).....129

6. Jumaniyozova Mamlakat Tojievna

XORAZM AHOLISINING XXI ASRNING BIRINCHI CHORAGIDA XALQ TABOVATI
"MAXFIY BILIMLARI" MASALASIGA MUNOSABATI YUZASIDAN KIBER ETNOLOGIK
VA ETNOGRAFIK DALA TADQIQOTI NATIJALARI.....135

7. Sheripov Umarbek Atajanovich ҚОРАҚУМ КАНАЛИНИНГ ҚУРИЛИШИ ВА УНИНГ МИНТАҚА ЭКОЛОГИЯСИГА САЛБИЙ ТАЪСИРИ.....	141
8. Маткаримова Садокат Максудовна, Абдуллаева Назокат Бахтияровна ХОРАЗМ КОРЕЙСЛАРИНИНГ ВИЛОЯТ ҚИШЛОҚ ХО‘ЖАЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДАГИ О‘РНИ.....	148
9. Abdirimov Zarifboy Erkinovich ХОРАЗМШОН – МА‘МУНИЛАР СУЛОЛАСИНИНГ БУЙУК ИПАК YO‘ЛИ SHIMOLIY TARMOG‘I ORQALI OLIB BORGAN SAVDO MUNOSABATLARI.....	154
10. Қурбонов Абдуллажон Атаназарович ҚУЙИ АМУДАРЁ ХУДУДИ ИЛК ЎРТА АСР ДАВРИ ТУРАР-ЖОЙЛАРИ ТАРИХШУНОСЛИГИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	160

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ATTITUDES OF TOURISTS TOWARDS ENVIRONMENTAL SOLUTIONS: A SURVEY OF TOURISTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to investigate the Attitudes of tourists towards environmental solutions: a survey of tourists in Uzbekistan. This study evaluates the attitudes of domestic and international tourists regarding the appropriate uses of national parks, as well as their environmental concerns. The study found that tourists' perceptions of the sustainability of green tourism and their environmental concerns significantly influenced their attitudes towards it. Additionally, our data showed that subjective norms have a significant negative impact on tourists' intentions to contribute to the sustainability of green tourism. In contrast, attitude has a considerable positive impact on these intentions. Furthermore, we found that environmental concerns and intentions to participate in green tourism significantly influence environmentally responsible tourist behavior.

Key words: sustainable development, green tourism, hotel industry, CO2 carbon footprint, global greenhouse gas emissions.

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ОТНОШЕНИЕ ТУРИСТОВ К ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИМ РЕШЕНИЯМ: ОПРОС ТУРИСТОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью исследования является изучение отношения туристов к экологическим решениям: опрос туристов в Узбекистане. Это исследование оценивает отношение внутренних и иностранных туристов к надлежащему использованию национальных парков, а также их экологические проблемы. Исследование показало, что восприятие туристами устойчивости зеленого туризма и их экологические проблемы значительно повлияли на их отношение к нему. Кроме того, наши данные показали, что субъективные нормы оказывают значительное негативное влияние на намерения туристов внести вклад в устойчивость зеленого туризма. Напротив, отношение оказывает значительное позитивное влияние на эти намерения. Кроме того, мы обнаружили, что экологические проблемы и намерения участвовать в зеленом туризме существенно влияют на экологически ответственное поведение туристов.

Ключевые слова: устойчивое развитие, зеленый туризм, гостиничная индустрия, углеродный след CO₂, глобальные выбросы парниковых газов.

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TURISTLARNING EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR YECHIMLARIGA MUNOSABATI: O‘ZBEKISTONDAGI TURISTLAR SO‘ROVNOMASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqot maqsadi sayyohlarning ekologik qarorlarga munosabatini o‘rganish: O‘zbekistondagi turistlar o‘rtasida so‘rovnoma o‘tkazish hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot mahalliy va xalqaro sayyohlarning milliy bog‘lardan to‘g‘ri foydalanishga, shuningdek, ularning ekologik muammolariga munosabatini baholashni tadqiq etishga bag‘ishlangan. Tadqiqot shuni ko‘rsatdiki, sayyohlarning yashil turizm barqarorligi haqidagi tasavvurlari va ularning ekologik tashvishlari unga bo‘lgan munosabatiga sezilarli ta‘sir ko‘rsatdi. Bundan tashqari, bizning ma‘lumotlarimiz sub‘ektiv me‘yorlar turistlarning yashil turizm barqarorligiga hissa qo‘shish niyatlariga sezilarli darajada salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatishini ko‘rsatdi. Aksincha, munosabat bu niyatlarga sezilarli ijobiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatdi. Bundan tashqari, biz ekologik tashvishlar va yashil turizm bilan shug‘ullanish niyatlari sayyohlarning ekologik jihatdan mas‘uliyatli xatti-harakatlariga sezilarli darajada ta‘sir qilishini aniqladik.

Kalit so‘zlar: barqaror rivojlanish, yashil turizm, mehmonxona sanoati, CO₂ uglerod izi, global issiqxona gazlari emissiyasi.

INTRODUCTION

Today, tourism is one of the largest and fastest growing economic sectors in the world due to its significant contribution to the national economy of countries around the world.

As a result of global climate change, international research, including a new travel report from Booking.com, found that “around 76% of travelers want to travel in a greener way in the next 12 months. About 81% of people are willing to change their travel behavior to reduce their impact on the environment. Almost two-thirds (63%) of tourists believe that booking sites, travel agencies and tour operators should disclose the CO₂ carbon footprint of the flights and other tourism products they offer. About 83% of Americans feel guilty about their previous trips, worrying that their trip was not eco-friendly [1].

As one of the fastest-growing industries, tourism has a significant impact on employment, income generation, and cultural development in host countries. According to recent statistics from the World Travel & Tourism Council, tourism's contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP) totaled \$8.27 trillion in 2017 and is expected to increase from 10.4% to 11.7% by 2028. The economic share will be \$12,450.1 billion after ten years, the direct share of this sector in the gross green product will be \$2,570.1 billion in 2017, and \$3,890 billion by 2028, i.e. 3.6% of the world's gross green product. is expected to form [2], tourism is responsible for roughly 8% of the world's carbon emissions [3]. The hotel sector should also actively participate in the realization of this large-scale goal.

The UN General Assembly unanimously approved the resolution “2027 - International Year of Sustainable and Viable Tourism”. The document was put forward by Uzbekistan and co-authored by more than 80 countries [4] and the main purpose of the document is based on Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s views expressed at the UN World Tourism Organization General Assembly session held in Samarkand in October 2023 regarding the stability and flexibility of the tourism sector in the face of new problems and modern threats, the report says.

The resolution affirms the principles that tourism plays an important role in preserving the rich cultural heritage of different civilizations, strengthening peace and tolerance, and respecting the values of peoples. Special attention is paid to the development of “green” tourism in order to preserve ecology, biodiversity and reduce atmospheric pollution.

The study is devoted to the consideration of one aspect of this large-scale topic - the influence of the hotel industry on green tourism, which determines the possibilities of its sustainable development, and the focus of the article is a comparative analysis of the state of green tourism, based on the identification of these features.

In recent decades, there has been an increasing concern about environmental issues, such as global warming, climate change, and the effects of greenhouse gases and pollution. These issues are largely attributed to human activities, including carbon emissions [5], excessive energy and water consumption, and the abuse of natural resources.

The tourism industry is a quickly growing sector and may end up as the major source of global greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). Its growth can be visualized as a matter of a double-edged sword in that tourism involves premium energy absorption, and massive contributions to waste generation and CO₂ emissions through its various functions and operations [6] on the one hand, and an essential source of economic growth and an enriching cultural base for communities on the other hand. For many years, research on tourism sustainability has increased greatly due to the major contribution of tourism to economic development, especially in cases of small island states that show consistent recent growth.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study used a simple random sampling method for data collection. Five five-star hotels in Uzbekistan were selected, and data was collected from these five hotels located in the three largest cities of the country. The focus of the study was on these five-star properties, as they were the only establishments known to engage in environmental initiatives. A structured questionnaire was used to gather information from guests at each hotel. Disproportionate simple random sampling was employed, with 20 questionnaires given to managers of each hotel, who then distributed them to guests. Managers handed out the questionnaires randomly at the hotel’s reception, allowing approximately 98.75% (214) of the questionnaires to be collected for further analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study examined whether there is a relationship between perceptions of green tourism, environmental concerns, subjective norms, attitudes, perceived behavioral control, intentions, and environmentally responsible behavior.

Table 1 The influence of age and gender of tourists on the development of green tourism.

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	110	51.41
	Male	104	48.59
Age	18-24 years	21	9.81
	25-34 years	39	18.22
	35-44 years	42	19.62
	45-54 years	43	20.11
	55-64 years	56	26.16
	65 years or older	13	6.08
Marital Status	Single	50	23.37
	Married	108	50.47
	Divorced/Widowed	56	26.16
Level of Education	High school	25	11.68
	Diploma	77	35.99
	Bachelor’s degree	95	44.39
	Master’s degree	9	4.2

	Doctoral degree	8	3.74
Family size	1 person	20	9.35
	2–3 persons	93	43.46
	4–5 persons	88	41.12
	More than 5 persons	13	6.07
Employment status	Student	26	12.15
	Housewife	43	20.1
	Unemployed	8	3.73
	Business	73	34.11
	Full-time	52	24.3
	Part-time	12	5.61

*Compiled by the author based on survey.

The population of this study was international tourists. In addition, in terms of level of education, a diploma (35.99%) was greater than a bachelor's degree (44.39%). Additionally, most of them had 2–3 persons in their family and most of them had full-time jobs (24.3%) and others were self-employed in business (34.11%), as presented in Table 1.

The conducted research touched only on some aspects of the extremely broad topic of green tourism development: attention was paid only to fixing the current situation, and the analysis of possible reasons that determine the specifics of individual objects was not exhaustive; rather, it made it possible to identify and explain some hypotheses that should be tested and clarified in subsequent works devoted to the problem under consideration.

CONCLUSION

This research aims to gain an overall understanding of the perception of green tourism among international visitors with regard to the improvement of environmental degradation. It also examines the sustainable approach of green tourism in the island and its impact on the behavioral aspects of visitors staying in five-star hotels in Uzbekistan.

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